

An IOT Based Smart Agricultural Field Monitoring and Irrigation System

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Abstract

Agriculture is given great importance as it is considered as a basic source of food, a financial source, aesthetics of the environment, limitation of soil erosion and air pollution. To maintain this importance, there are many problems that must be solved such as prolonged droughts, reliance on rain only for irrigation of crops and lack of advanced and modern technological methods in agriculture, etc., so, proposing a smart watering system depends on the Internet of Things (IOT). The system is proposed to save time, water, money and farmer power. It irrigates the plants by driving adopted pump via volt per hertz (V/F) scalar method. This method controls the speed of induction motor (pump) by varying both the frequency and voltage of the applied source in a fixed V / F ratio depending on an external analog control voltage (processed data of soil moisture). Therefore, the motor's torque is kept constant due to the stability of magnetic flux across the whole speed range. The pump speed control adjusts the water flow rate automatically according to soil moisture data. Notifications and the sensed data are sent to mobile users (farmers) periodically. Farmers can monitor field conditions on any spot by creating an application in the user's mobile phone.

Keywords: Irrigation, Internet of Things, V/F Scalar Method, Variable Frequency Drive, Soil Moisture Sensor

1. Introduction

Soil is the first environment for plant growth, and fertility is the most important feature of the soil in order to be suitable for cultivation. One of the most important factors for the success and establishment of agriculture is an irrigation technique that aims to distribute water among all plants in specific and hesitant quantities that can satisfy the daily needs of plants. There are two basic methods of watering. The first and rudimentary method is the one that requires a lot of time, money and workers (farmers). The second is a method of watering the plants

automatically, and this is done by applying several types of modern technologies.

Recently, automatic irrigation methods have been developed as part of modern technology. Modern irrigation can be done by planting sensors on the farmland and near the roots of the plants. These sensors can monitor the water needed by the plants and provide smart irrigation that saves time, water, etc. The sensors will also provide information about the soil and its fertility.

Currently, irrigation has become one of the important areas relying on the Internet of things. In this context,

in 2018, [1], T. Thamaraimanalan and others, proposed a system consisting of ESP8266 (NodeMCU) as a system brain connected to three sensors; namely, moisture sensor, (temperature & humidity) sensor, and ultrasonic sensor. These sensors send the data to ESP8266 which includes a Wi-Fi technology. A simple switch in the android application will turn the watering process when the user receives the indication to irrigate the garden. In 2018, [2], S Nalini Durga, M Ramakrishna, implemented a system to monitor the soil moisture, temperature, air humidity and water level for irrigation controlling. The sensors readings are send to the cloud server for decision and storing for controlling actions in the future. In 2017, [3], Alok Gora and M.S. Dulawat, introduced a system for smart irrigation powered by solar array using moisture sensor. The sensed data is adopted for controlling actions and also indicates the user using GSM. In 2018, [4] Dr. M.Yuvaraju, K. J. Priyanga, proposed an automatic irrigation system includes sensor network distributed using moisture, temperature, humidity sensors and sensor of water level. When the soil is dry, the watering system is on and it stops when the soil is wet. This system can be settled by sending data to mobile and monitor.

In 2018, [5] Chethan.R and other, designed a system to control and monitor the moisture content in the soil using LabVIEW and show the measurements of the sensor on the webpage using IOT technique. In 2018, [6] Gaikwad Tararani and other, proposed a system used raspberry, moisture, temperature, humidity, rain sensors. The sensor senses the value and sends it to the raspberry pi which is used to send the value to the web server and then the web server compares between the sensed value and the current value of the raspberry pi. Thus, the result values send to perform the control action. In 2018, [7], Sharmin Akter and other, proposed a system uses Arduino and sensor technology with, DC motor, relay and battery. This system acts as a smart switching system that senses the moisture of the soil and if necessary, the plants are irrigated. The motor is ON or OFF depends on the value of the moisture sensor. In 2019, [8], Dr. Sanjay N. Patil1, Madhuri B. Jadhav2, proposed a system includes several sensors such as humidity, temperature, rain detector and soil moisture. It collected data from field and processed. The sensors are combined with web technology to control and monitor the sensors data. The system sends the sensor data to the user to take controlling action using actuator.

The proposed system focuses on monitoring and irrigation of plants automatically using IOT technique. And the approved watering pump gives

variable water flow rate depending on the soil moisture data processing.

2. Theoretical Background

A. Water Flow Rate Control Via V/F Scalar Method

The submersible pump has three important variables: flow rate (Q), head (H), and speed (N). By changing the speed of the pump, the other two variables can be controlled due to the fact that flow rate is proportional to the speed, and the head of the water is proportional to the square of the speed as in the equations (1) and (2) [9].

$$\frac{Q_{old}}{Q_{new}} = \left(\frac{N_{old}}{N_{new}}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{H_{old}}{H_{new}} = \left(\frac{N_{old}}{N_{new}}\right)^2 \quad (2)$$

Equation (3) shows that the pump power (P) is proportional to the cube speed.

$$\frac{P_{old}}{P_{new}} = \left(\frac{N_{old}}{N_{new}}\right)^3 \quad (3)$$

The relationship curves of equations above are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 The characteristic curves of water pump

From equations (1) and (3) one can say that the water flow rate can be controlled by adjusting the pump speed, and that is done by changing the applied electrical power of the pump. In this research work, the input power can be controlled by applying a variable frequency voltage signal as a control signal using Variable Frequency Drive (VFD). VFD is also called Variable Voltage Variable Frequency (VVVF) drive, Variable Speed Drive (VSD) or inverter. It is a device can be adopted to control the submersible pump speed and thus controlling water flow rate.

The VFD unit consists of four main stages as shown in Fig 2. The first stage is a rectifier used to convert AC voltage to DC one. The second is a DC link stage to make rectifier output smooth DC voltage. The third stage is a controlled inverter to convert constant DC voltage to variable AC voltage. The last stage is a control circuit through which the AC output can be controlled depending on an external control signal applied to it.

Figure 2 VFD unit components

There are many benefits offered by the VFDs. These include:

- Electrical power saving.
- Procedures of shutdown and start up control.
- Proper pump work and at best points of efficiency.
- Reduction of the main voltage drawn at start up on power lines.
- Pump speed control to deliver accurate water heads or flow rates.
- Pump can be remotely controlled using IOT with the support of Wi-Fi Microcontroller.

Practically the speed of an induction motor varies from theoretical speed (no load speed) to practical speed (full load speed) and this variation is small. Also the active speed of the motor shaft is close but not equal to the revolving magnetic field speed. Thus, controlling the magnetic field speed leads to controlling the shaft speed. The revolving magnetic field speed (N_s) is a function of the applied voltage frequency (F_i) and it is given by the equation (4):

$$N_s = \frac{120F_i}{2P} \tag{4}$$

Where P is the half number of poles.

In constant Volt/Hz ratio method of operating the VFD unit, the formula between the control signal V_{cont} (which has a range [0V to 10V] in the adopted HYUNDAI brand of VFD) and the VFD output frequency (F_o) is :

$$F_o = K * V_{cont} \tag{5}$$

Thus from equations (4) and (5), the shaft speed (N_r) can be written approximately as :

$$N_r = \frac{K * V_{cont}}{V_{cont}} \tag{6}$$

Figure 3 below shows the configuration of constant V/F control method to drive water pump by applying adjustable frequency voltage signal as a pump input. This is done by convert the control voltage to power frequency and voltage. These values are adopted to generate the single phase voltage with phase shift 90 degree between each other. So, this signals can be used to generate the Pulse Width Generating (PWM) signals by comparing them with a triangular signal has a higher magnitude and a frequency to overcome the over-modulating. These PWM signal are used to set of Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor (IGBT) in inverter stage to generate variable voltage variable frequency output signals to driven the pump.

Figure 3 Configuration of constant V/F control method

B. Internet of Things (IOT)

The Internet of Things is a newly emerging term, meaning the new technology that allows the connected devices to communicate with each other via the internet. These devices include tools, sensors, artificial intelligence tools, and others. This technique is distinguished by allowing a person to be free from the place, meaning that a person can control tools without having to be in a specific place to deal with a specific device.

The concept of the Internet of Things shows how the World Wide Web will affect the world in the near future. Most electronic devices will become autonomous and do not need any human intervention. These devices will be able to report their faults themselves and fix them, and the concept will expand to include everything that comes to mind, in

agriculture, industry and various other areas of life for example, self-driving cars, the lighting system in the home, etc.

In IOT-based smart agriculture, a crop field monitoring system can be implemented with the help of sensors (light, temperature, soil moisture, etc.). Farmers can monitor field conditions on any spot. On environmental issues, smart agriculture can provide great benefits, including using water more efficiently, or improving inputs and treatments. Figure 4 shows proposed IOT-based smart agriculture system.

Figure 4 Proposed IOT-based smart agriculture system

3. Proposed System

A. System Implementation

The block diagram of the proposed system is shown in Fig.5.

Figure 5 block diagram of proposed IoT-based irrigation system

The system consists of the following components:

1. ESP-32 Wi-Fi Microcontroller
2. Four Moisture Soil Sensors
3. Four 5V Relays
4. Four 12V ON/OFF Valve
5. 20X4 LCD
6. I2C Board
7. Inverter (VFD)
8. Submersible Water Pump

From figure 5, the idea of the proposed system focuses on splitting the soil into four miniature regions, each one with a sensor to measure soil moisture and a solenoid valve to allow passage or blocking of water. The soil moisture sensors are connected to the Wi-Fi microcontroller. The microcontroller reads the data from the sensors and sends them via Wi-Fi technique to the mobile phone to be displayed through an application designed for this purpose. At same time, user can monitor the sensed data in the field because the system is also equipped with 20X4 LCD. If the soil moisture of any region decreases, the valve of this region will be activated and at the same time the microcontroller activates the VFD unit and turns ON the pump using V/F scalar method. Also the microcontroller can send notifications to a mobile phone when any region of the soil needs water.

1. ESP-32 Wi-Fi Microcontroller

ESP-32 is a chip microcontroller board integrated with Wi-Fi and Bluetooth techniques. It is low power and low cost. It has 16 channels x 12-bit as Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) pins and two channels x 8-bit as Digital to Analog Converter (DAC) pins. ESP-32 has two Xtensa® 32-bit LX6 microprocessors with 80 MHz and 160 MHz clock frequency. Figure 6 shows the ESP-32 WiFi/Microcontroller board.

Figure 6 ESP-32 WiFi/Microcontroller board

2. Moisture Soil Sensors

FC-28 Soil moisture sensor measures the water volumetric content inside the soil. It gives the moisture level as an output. This sensor can be connected with both digital and analog output. Figure 7 shows the FC-28 soil moisture sensor.

Figure 7 FC-28 soil moisture sensor.

3. 5V Relays

Relay can be used to control the 12V DC valve by switching it ON and OFF according to the 5V-12V control signal from a microcontroller. Relay is shown in Fig.8.

Figure 8 5V Relay

4. 12V ON/OFF Valve

A solenoid valve is an electrical valve that is used to pass or stop water flow. The valve is controlled by an electrical current that turns on the coil, which generates a magnetic field to open or lock the water path.

Figure 9 12V ON/OFF Valve

5. 20X4 LCD

The 2004A LCD Module is designed to display letters, numbers and symbols, in a raster manner. It can display 4 lines, each containing 20 characters. These screens support receiving data, either 4-bit or 8-bit. They generate letters through a built-in memory for letter shapes and draw them within the framework of a 7 * 5 bitmap system.

The most important technical specifications of the screen are Operating voltage 5 V Display area (length * width) 76 * 26mm The screen color is blue. The operating temperature is -20 to +70 degrees Celsius. Figure 10 shows the 20X4 LCD.

Figure 10 20X4 LCD

6. I2C Board

This board is adopted to reduce the number of pins used by the microcontroller to operate the displays, allowing a lot of number of inputs and outputs to be connected using the I2C connection. I2C is a protocol that allows the operation of a group of components or devices using the fewest electronic connections possible and with the same efficiency. This protocol allows the operation and exchange of data with all devices through two wires only or, more correctly, through two signals. Serial data line, serial serial line.

Figure 11 I2C Board

7. Inverter (VFD)

An inverter is a device used to control the speed of AC motors from the moment they are turned on until turned off over its normal operating period. The device controls the speed of the motor by changing the voltage and frequency of the wave applied to the motor windings, and this is done by converting the AC voltage feeding the VFD to the DC voltage by using rectifier and electrolytic capacitors and then converting it to an AC frequency wave through a set of transistors, usually of the type Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor IGBT. The voltage and frequency effective values of this wave can be controlled by controlling the firing rate of these transistors until the required speed is achieved.

In this work, VFD is adopted to control the pump speed and thus the water flow rate. It has been programmed by constant V/F ratio to be able to changing water flow rate according to an external control voltage signal represented soil moisture readings.

Figure 12 Inverter (VFD) unit

8. Submersible Water Pump

A submersible pump, like any other pump, is used to transfer water from one point to another. The main difference between a submersible pump and any other type is that it is completely immersed in the water to be pumped. This pump can be used in many pumping applications. In the current work, a submersible pump was adopted to match the presence of submersible pump in river or pond to push the water into the agricultural field. Fig. 13 below shows the adopted 220V supply and 2500 Liter per hour flow rate.

Figure 13 submersible water pump.

B. System Software

At the beginning, the soil moisture is read by ESP-32 microcontroller. This microcontroller has been programmed as follow: If the moisture value becomes less than a certain value, the ESP-32 Microcontroller will activate a relay to turn on the valve. At the same time, the VFD operates and makes the pump turn on according to the soil moisture data. All the sensors data are sent to both the mobile application and the LCD. Figure 14 shows the flowchart of the control process according to the adopted software code.

Figure 14 shows the flowchart of the control process Table 1 shows the programming of the VFD unit which has been programmed by the constant V/F control method. In this method, the programming should be direct proportional between the applied voltage and frequency of the pump as in the blue relationship curve in Fig. 15. So, this curve can be set by programming the VFD parameters as shown in Table1.

Table 1: Programming of VFD unit

Parameter	Name	Setting
F02	Acceleration time	0.1 sec
F03	Deceleration time	0.1 sec
F04	Direction of rotation	0
A01	Frequency command	1
A02	Run command	0
A03	Base frequency Setting	50Hz
A04	Maximum frequency setting	50Hz
A05	Start of external frequency	0Hz
A06	End of external frequency	50Hz
A07	Start of control input	0 V
A08	End of control input	3.3 V
A09	Sampling setting of external frequency	1
A031	V/F curve characteristic (Constant Torque)	0

Figure 15 V/F pattern

4. Results

The practical circuit of adopted system is shown in Fig.16.

Figure 16 Overall practical circuit of adopted system

Figure 17 shows the user’s mobile application, which displays soil moisture data for all sensors. The first soil region has 58% moisture content, the second soil has 22% moisture content, the third soil has 90% moisture content and the fourth soil has 91% moisture content. Also the readings of all these sensors can be monitor on the 20X4 LCD as shown in figure 18 below.

The mobile application of the user can give the notification if any soil needs to water when the soil moisture reading is less than 30%. From the results above, the second sensor read 22% moisture, so the message must be displayed in application as shown in Fig.19.

Figure 17 The user’s mobile application, which displays soil moisture data for all sensors.

Figure 18 Readings of all sensors displayed on 20X4 LCD

Figure 19 Indication of the soil needs water

It is known that the sensor is a device that converts the physical signal into an electrical one. The figure 20 below shows the output of the sensor as a voltage signal whereas the physical signal represents soil moisture (loamy sand soil has been adopted). It is possible to see from the relationship curve that the greatest voltage is 3.3 which can be obtained when the moisture is 100% and vice versa.

Figure 20 Soil moisture vs it's effective voltage

The curve in figure 21 illustrates the relationship between the soil moisture and water flow (note: the water flow is found out by measuring the rotational speed of the pump due to a direct proportionality between them as shown in Figure 1 and Equation 1). In this figure it is possible to note that the pump will give the greatest flow of water if the soil is dry and vice versa.

Figure 21 Relationship between the soil moisture and water flow

The soil moisture readings are taken from Digital to Analog Converter (DAC) output pin after being processed in ESP-32. So, the relationship curve between the output of DAC and the applied effective frequency or voltage values of the pump is given in figure 22 below. Hence, the pump frequency or voltage increases as the soil moisture decreases and vice versa.

Figure 22 Relationship curve between the output of DAC and the applied effective frequency or voltage values of the pump

Figure 23 shows the relationship between the pump frequency and the flow rate. According to figure, when the pump frequency increases, the flow rate increases as well because the pump frequency leads to an increase in the pump speed and thus the water flow rate increases and vice versa

Figure 23 Relationship curve between the pump frequency and the flow rate.

5. Conclusion

In this work a smart monitoring and watering system based on the Internet of Things has been implemented. The system has given very satisfactory results for the sensors data sent through the Internet and they are identical to the results displayed on the monitoring LCD in the field. Also the characteristics of the pump have been studied when the soil moisture changed, and by adopting constant V/F

control method using VFD unit, the results were realistic and satisfactory as well.

6. References

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